

Synthesis and Characterization of Bis-Acetylacetonatozink (II) [(Zn(acac)₂(H₂O)]

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ABSTRACT: The synthesis of the bis-acetylacetonate zink (II) monohydrate complex [Zn(acac)₂(H₂O)] has been conducted. FTIR analysis, TGA-DSC, and SEM micrographic analysis performed complex characterization. The yield of the complex compound [Zn(acac)₂(H₂O)] was 36.24% using NaOH as a pH regulator. Based on the FTIR characterization of the typical absorption complex [Zn(acac)₂(H₂O)] appears at 763.88 cm⁻¹ for Zn-O, C-H at 933.9 cm⁻¹ and 1020 cm⁻¹, C=C and C=O at 1516 cm⁻¹, 1610 cm⁻¹ and OH at 3450 cm⁻¹ respectively. Thermal analysis of the complex shows that the decomposition temperature was obtained at 186°C. Based on the micrographic results, the complex has a non-uniform surface relief. The complex has an even distribution of pores with non-uniform pore sizes. Zn particles are deposited on the complex surface with various sizes to produce pores on the solid surface.

KEYWORDS: acetylacetonate, bis-acetylacetonates (II), complex compound.

INTRODUCTION

The advancement of research on complex compounds or coordination compounds has emerged as a compelling subject, given the broad-ranging applications of these compounds across various domains. For instance, in healthcare, complex compounds serve as contrast agents in Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), thereby aiding in the enhancement of tissue visualization (Chen et al., 2022). In magnetic materials, complex compounds find utility as thin-film-free sensors (Baran et al., 2020). Concurrently, complex compounds are harnessed within the industrial sector for corrosion inhibition purposes (Zaidi et al., 2023).

Complex compounds can be synthesized by reacting ligands, which are bases with free electron pairs, with metals, which act as electron pair acceptors donated by the ligands. Acetylacetonone (2,4-pentanedione) is a β-keto compound that can ionize as a weak acid, forming the acetylacetonate anion, forming six-membered ring bidentate complexes with oxygen donor ligands. Oxygen is commonly used as an organic ligand in synthesizing complex compounds (Saria et al., 2012).

Based on research conducted by inorganic researchers, transition metals have been extensively studied and synthesized into complex compounds (Soofivand et al., 2014). This is attributed to transition metals' inert and stable nature in forming complex compounds with various ligands, one of which is the acetylacetonone ligand. Several previous studies have successfully synthesized Metal-acetylacetonone complexes (M-acac), such as bis-acetylacetonone nickel (II) complex (Mintari et al., 2015), bis-acetylacetonone copper (II) complex (Paramitha et al., 2014), cobalt acetylacetonate complex (Saria et al., 2012), tris-aluminium acetylacetonate (Borker et al., 2010), tris-bis(acetylacetonone) cobalt (II) complex (Gnanasoundari & Natarajan, 2005), and modified zinc/MgO-acetylacetonone complex (Matsushashi, 2022).

The synthesis technique of complex compounds is relatively more straightforward than inorganic materials or organic compounds. Unlike several previous studies, for the synthesis of metal acetylacetonate complexes, techniques such as the volatile phase technique (Feng et al., 2022), precipitation method (Petrović et al., 2015), Ultrasonic Chemical Spray (Biswal et al., 2014), and hydrolysis (Petrović et al., 2014) have been employed. However, in this study, the synthesis process was conducted solely through conventional chemical reactions and ligand-metal complexation processes, forming complex compounds. This research focuses on synthesizing zinc complex compounds with bidentate acetylacetonate ligands. Furthermore, FTIR, SEM, and TGA-DSC analysis characterize the synthesized complex compounds.

METHODS

Materials and Equipment

The instruments utilized in this research included a Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer (FT-IR spectrometer; Perkin Elmer) with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and a KBr pellet with a wavenumber range of $400\text{-}5000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM), EVOMA 10, was employed to observe the morphology of the synthesized products. Thermal analysis was conducted using TGA PT 6000 and DSC PT 1600. The materials used in this study consisted of $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck), acetylacetonate (Sigma Aldrich), NaOH (Merck), and ethyl acetate.

Synthesis of Bis-acetylacetonate Zinc (II) Complex

The bis-acetylacetonate zinc (II) complex was synthesized by modifying the method (Brahma & Shivashankar, 2015). A solution of acetylacetonate was added with NaOH as a pH regulator and reacted with a solution of $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$. This mixture was then heated at 60°C for 1 hour. Subsequently, the solution was cooled until a precipitate formed. The precipitate was then filtered and subjected to crystallization with ethyl acetate. The bis-acetylacetonate zinc (II) complex appeared as white crystalline solids. The procedure was repeated using methanol and acetone as pH regulators to determine the optimal yield. The product with the highest yield was further characterized.

Figure 1. Scheme of Bis-acetylacetonate zinc (II) Complex Formation

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The synthesis of zinc metal with acetylacetonate ligand in NaOH, methanol, and chloroform solvent yields a white crystalline precipitate. The yield of the bis-acetylacetonate zinc (II) complex compound $[\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ can be seen in Table 1. The percentage yield of the complex in NaOH solvent is the highest in this study, at 36.24%. This is to the previous report by (Hayami et al., 2014) that bis-acetylacetonate zinc (II) complex is a white crystalline material that can be synthesized with NaOH as a pH regulator with a %yield reaching 88%. The yields of bis-acetylacetonate zinc (II) synthesis using different pH regulators are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. yields of bis-acetylacetonate zinc (II)

No	Compounds	% Yield
1	Bis-asetilasetonatozink (II)@ NaOH	36.24
2	Bis-asetilasetonatozink (II)@Metanol	24.21
3	Bis-asetilasetonatozink (II)@Kloroform	18.96

The FTIR analysis of the complex compound $[\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ is conducted in the wavenumber range of $500\text{-}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to determine the functional groups of the complex compound and the interactions that occur between Zn and acetylacetonate. The indication of the formation of the complex compound $[\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ is the appearance of characteristic absorptions of the functional groups of the complex $[\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$, such as Zn-O absorption at the wavenumbers of $650\text{-}760\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Ambrožič et al., 2010), aliphatic C-H absorption at the wavenumbers of 927 cm^{-1} and 2979 cm^{-1} (Chesnokov & Rostovtseva, 2019), C=C and C=O absorptions at the wavenumbers of 1400 cm^{-1} , 1650 cm^{-1} , and broad hydroxyl group absorption at the wavenumber of 3500 cm^{-1} (Brahma & Shivashankar, 2015). From the FTIR analysis results of the synthesized complex compound, as shown in Figure 2, it can be observed that there is a broad absorption from O-H appearing at the wavenumber of 3450 cm^{-1} , indicating that the bis-acetylacetonate zinc (II) complex binds water molecules. According to the research (Musić et al., 2010), the Zn-acetylacetonate complex will bind one water molecule, forming a pentacoordinate structure adopted from a square pyramidal structure.

Figure 2. FTIR Spectrum of Bis-acetylacetonate zinc (II) Complex

The Zn-O absorption appears at the wavenumber of 763.88 cm⁻¹, and C-H absorption occurs at 933.9 cm⁻¹ and 1020 cm⁻¹. Meanwhile, C=C and C=O absorptions appear at 1516 cm⁻¹ and 1610 cm⁻¹ respectively.

Figure 3. Thermal analysis of bis-acetylacetonate zinc(II) complex using TGA-DSC

Thermal analysis using TGA (Figure 3) reveals a single-stage mass decomposition originating from the precursor complex [Zn(acac)₂(H₂O)]. Mass decomposition initiates with the loss of water molecules at temperatures ranging from 40 to 120°C. Significant mass decomposition occurs at 150°C with a total percentage mass loss of 46.4%. This phenomenon indicates that the [Zn(acac)₂(H₂O)] complex exhibits considerable stability against heat. Based on the DSC analysis results (Figure 3), an exothermic peak is observed at 186°C, corresponding to the decomposition temperature of the [Zn(acac)₂(H₂O)] complex. These findings align with previous research, which reported the decomposition temperature of the [Zn(acac)₂(H₂O)] complex to be within the range of 136-220°C (Brahma & Shivashankar, 2015).

Figure 4. Micrograph analysis using SEM of bis-acetylacetonate zinc(II) complex

Continuing from the micrograph analysis results aided by SEM (Figure 4), it is observed that the $[\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ complex exhibits a non-uniform surface relief. The complex demonstrates a uniform distribution of pores with non-uniform pore sizes. Zinc particles are deposited on the surface of the complex with varying sizes, thus resulting in surface pores on the solid. This condition allows the $[\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ complex to possess low stability and susceptibility to hydrolysis. Numerous researchers have exploited these properties to utilize the $[\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ complex as a precursor material in zinc oxide synthesis (Šarić et al., 2019).

CONCLUSION

The synthesis of bis-acetylacetonate zinc (II) complex monohydrate $[\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ has been successfully achieved. The yield of the complex compound $[\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ obtained is 36.24% using NaOH as the pH regulator. Based on the FTIR characterization, characteristic absorption bands of the $[\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ complex appear at wave numbers of 763.88 cm^{-1} for Zn-O, absorption of C-H appears at wave numbers of 933.9 cm^{-1} and 1020 cm^{-1} , C=C and C=O absorption occur at wave numbers of 1516 cm^{-1} and 1610 cm^{-1} , respectively, while OH appears at a wave number of 3450 cm^{-1} . Based on TGA and DSC characterization, the zinc bis-acetylacetonate complex (II) monohydrate $[\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ demonstrates sufficient thermal stability, with complex decomposition occurring at 186°C . Micrograph analysis using SEM reveals that the complex exhibits evenly distributed pores with non-uniform pore sizes.

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